

I had good resistance to three isolates of BB as well as good agronomic traits and high yield potential.

Reaction of the Guangdong differentials to different isolates of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* are given in Table 2. On the basis of these reactions, most of the isolates from Fuyang tested so far belong to groups IV, II, and I. Group IV, virulent on China differentials, was often collected from local popularized varieties. BB was scored by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* at 14 and 21 d after inoculation.

Table 2. Virulence of 3 pathotypes of *X. c. pv. oryzae* collected in Fuyang during 1987 on Chinese rice differentials.^a

Isolate	Reaction					Group
	IR26	Nongkeng 57	Zhaiyeqing 8	Baotaiyai	Jinggong 30	
CN-X1	HR	R	MR	S	HS	II
CN-X3	HR	MR	MR	MR	S	I
CN-X12	MR	HS	HS	HS	HS	IV

^a Ratings based on lesion length and mean lesion length for 20 inoculated leaves. SES 0-9 scale. R (resistant) = 1, MR (moderately resistant) = 3, S (susceptible) = 7, HS (highly susceptible) = 9.

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Scoring systems for evaluating rice varietal resistance to bacterial blight (BB): scales for different growth stages

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BB lesion development in rice varies by variety and plant growth stage. The scale as well as time of scoring to assess varietal resistance is influenced by plant age. We attempted to formulate a realistic scoring system for BB at different stages of plant growth. Planting and lesion measurement were the same as in the first study.

Our observation showed that lesions on susceptible varieties inoculated at 20 d after sowing (DAS) reached maximum level at 11 d after inoculation (DAI). Inoculation at 30 DAS produced the most lesions at 11-41 DAI; that at 40 DAS, 11-17 DAI; and that at 50 DAS, 17-20 DAI. Actual lesion area, apparent infection rate, and relative area under disease progression curve (ADPC) were analyzed. Final disease ratings and relative ADPCs followed a similar sequence in lesion area. The infection rates, however, did not follow such sequence, compared to actual disease rating or to relative ADPCs.

Final disease ratings and relative ADPCs were further tested to categorize the level of resistance among the test

Table 1. Varietal resistance to PXO61 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, using different scales at 20 DAS. IRRI, 1988.

Variety	Leaf area infected (%)		Relative ADPC		SES scale	
	11 DAI	14 DAI	11 DAI	14 DAI	11 DAI	14 DAI
RP4-2	93.60	100.0	0.232	0.390	9	9
TN1	89.10	99.8	0.230	0.383	9	9
59-439 (BII/MAS)	92.53	100.0	0.218	0.378	9	9
6-1	89.13	98.1	0.210	0.365	9	9
IR24	87.70	98.0	0.199	0.355	9	9
Milyang 23	88.60	98.4	0.193	0.352		
CAS209	84.30	99.2	0.193	0.348	9	9
BG94-1	82.63	96.8	0.188	0.340	9	9
Khao Khao Nhay	78.60	90.0	0.186	0.327	9	9
MTU18	78.90	97.7	0.181	0.332	9	9
IR8	77.77	98.7	0.179	0.330	9	9
Yakai	77.87	98.6	0.175	0.327	9	9
Aneira	75.40	92.4	0.169	0.313		9
Binirnal	75.53	98.6	0.166	0.317	9	9
Pyi Daw Aye	75.20	93.9	0.165	0.311	9	9
Kyeearni	80.07	96.0	0.165	0.318	9	9
Zenith	63.10	76.3	0.155	0.274	9	9
ASE Pute Rono	58.17	76.2	0.147	0.259	9	9
Pale Angga	59.57	85.3	0.141	0.266	9	9
Yolle	66.93	91.5	0.139	0.279	9	9
Kauk Hnyin	64.50	90.7	0.137	0.274	9	9
Banda Merah	62.17	78.7	0.136	0.258	9	9
Gaukkyi	51.50	85.9	0.133	0.228	9	9
Ketan Jimbruk	41.30	49.9	0.100	0.176	7	7
Pae Moku	39.60	64.2	0.091	0.183	7	9
Tahun Gembrong	33.53	39.2	0.088	0.143	7	7
Ketan Ireng	20.30	25.5	0.055	0.092	6	7
Meegauk	22.67	32.1	0.055	0.102	5	7
Akundi	17.70	25.0	0.041	0.078	5	5
Warangal Culture 1263	14.80	23.1	0.040	0.072	5	5
Sankurcha	9.07	13.7	0.022	0.041	5	5
IR20	7.33	10.8	0.020	0.035	5	5
IR22	5.83	9.3	0.017	0.029	5	5
DZ78	6.57	13.8	0.013	0.032	5	5
AUS40	5.13	9.0	0.012	0.024	5	5
AUS463	3.60	5.3	0.008	0.016	3	3
IR1545	3.37	4.4	0.008	0.014	3	3
AUS338	3.57	6.3	0.008	0.016	3	5
Makhmal Mehi	1.00	1.8	0.002	0.005	3	3
DV85	0.53	1.2	0.002	0.003	1	3

varieties. A scale for each growth stage was adapted from the Horsfall-Barrett scale based on visual estimation of tissue area infection, widely used in plant pathology. The Horsfall-Barrett scale is based on proportion of disease intensity and has 12 divisions. When it was used to rate disease based on actual lesion area, the score of 1 was excluded.

The modified scale, also based on percent lesion area, has 9 instead of 12 divisions: 1 = 1-3% lesion area, 2 = 4-6%, 3 = 7-12%, 4 = 13-25%, 5 = 26-50%, 6 = 51-75%, 7 = 76-87%, 8 = 88-94%, and 9 = 95-100%. It is suitable for scoring disease level at 11-14 DAI on plants 20-30 DAS (Table 1).

At late to maximum tillering (40-50 DAS) final disease ratings and relative ADPCs agree with each other, but not with apparent infection rates. A different scale was developed to score these growth stages at 14-17 DAI: 1 = < 1%, 2 = 1-2%, 3 = 3-4%, 4 = 5-8%, 5 = 9-16%, 6 = 17-32%, 7 = 33-40%, 8 = 41-50%, 9 = > 50%. The modified scale for plants from maximum tillering to maturity also was suitable for evaluating varietal resistance to BB (Table 2).

For the purpose of field screening, the current *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) scoring is adequate to distinguish resistance from susceptibility.

Table 2. Varietal resistance to BB measured by 3 different scales. IRRI, 1988.

Variety	Relative ADPC value	Leaf area infected (%)	SES scale	Modified scale (1 to 9)
IR910143-6-1	0.128	45.47	7	9
TN1	0.127	44.37	7	9
IR24	0.125	42.33	7	8
MTU18	0.110	41.90	7	8
Khao Khao Nhay	0.108	36.50	7	7
Milyang 23	0.107	33.43	7	7
RP4-2	0.104	34.87	7	7
IR8	0.098	30.43	7	6
Binirnal	0.084	30.43	7	6
CAS209	0.076	27.30	7	6
Aneira	0.074	27.12	7	6
59439 (B11/MAS)	0.065	26.80	7	6
BG94-1	0.062	24.87	5	6
Yakai	0.061	24.70	5	6
Yolle	0.057	21.83	5	6
Pyi Daw Aye	0.050	18.50	5	6
Zenith	0.049	12.67	5	5
ASE Pute Rono	0.043	15.23	5	5
Pale Angga	0.043	14.23	5	5
Band Merah	0.039	14.23	5	5
Kauk Hnyin	0.031	14.80	5	5
Ketan Jimbruk	0.030	9.20	5	5
Gaukkyi	0.027	11.40	5	5
Pae Moku	0.024	9.17	5	5
Akundi	0.015	5.47	5	4
Tahun Gembrong	0.013	4.17	5	3
Warangal Culture 1263	0.011	4.03	3	3
Meegauk	0.1010	4.03	3	3
IR20	0.008	2.60	3	3
AUS40	0.005	2.23	3	2
Sankurcha	0.009	1.80	3	2
IR22	0.004	1.33	3	2
AUS338	0.004	1.17	5	2
DZ78	0.004	1.33	3	2
IR1545	0.003	1.00	3	2
Makhmal Mehi	0.003	1.00	3	2
AUS463	0.003	0.87	1	1
DV85	0.002	0.60	1	1

Sources of resistance to *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. in Nepal

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Blast epidemics at the seedling stage are frequent in different parts of Nepal. Varieties resistant to *P. oryzae* become susceptible within a few years. To find new sources of resistance, we reviewed varietal reactions in the International Rice Blast Nurseries at Kankai, Parwanipur, Khumaltar, and Palung 1983-85. These locations cover a wide range of climatic conditions (plain, midhill, and high hill).

Sources of broad-spectrum resistance to *P. oryzae* Cav. in Nepal.

Rice line ^a	Donor parents ^b
C1322-28	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR7473-118-2-2	Tadukan, Sigadis, Tetep
IR9852-22-3	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR13240-108-2-2	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR17525-278-1-1 ^c	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR18348-36-3-3	Tadukan, Sigadis, Tetep
IR18349-22-1-2	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR19672-140-2-3	Tadukan, Sigadis
IR21820-154-3-2	Tadukan, Sigadis, Tetep
Iri 360	unknown

^a All were resistant in Kankai (plain, 1984-85), Parwanipur (plain, 1983-85), Khumaltar (mid-hill, 1983-85), and Palung (high hill, 1983-84). Scoring was done according to the Standard evaluation system for rice scale of 0-9: 0-2 = resistant (R). ^b Extracted from *Parentages of IRRI crosses, IRI to IR50,000*. ^c Data not available for Parwanipur, 1985.

Disease pressure was high at all locations. A large number of rice lines exhibited resistance reaction in 1 or 2 tests, but only 10 lines were resistant in 2 to 3 yr at all sites (see table). Nine were progeny of Tadukan, Sigadis, and Tetep. These donor parents also exhibited resistance at all test sites.

Changes in disease reaction of several international differentials indicate the existence of different physiological races of the blast pathogen and unstable resistance in released varieties. Some of the lines identified that have desirable agronomic traits might be sources of resistance to control leaf blast epidemics at the seedling stage. □